

“LINGUO-PRAGMATIC WAYS OF EXPRESSIONS LINKED TO FOOD IN ENGLISH, FRENCH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES”

Sufiyev Hakimjon Xusanboy o‘g‘li

E-mail: hsufiyev@bk.ru.

ABSTRACT

Culture, being national, is to a large extent connected with the nature and patterns of immanent development, the specifics of the internal system and other features of a particular language. The national-cultural layer is the most important semantic basis of any language. In different linguistic and cultural communities in relation to the same phenomena, in particular, to objects of material culture, various national stereotypes are formed.

Key words: semantics, symbolism, culture related language, allomorphic features, lexico-semantic, extralinguistic world.

Language and culture are an interdependent bilateral entity. Language is a specific linguoculturological phenomenon. It absorbs all the richness of culture. E. Sapir wrote: “Culture is a socially inherited complex of ways of activity and beliefs that make up the fabric of our life” (Sapir E. 2001, p. 437).

One and the same reality, a phenomenon can and does have in different cultures, if not different, then different semantics, symbolism, comprehension and can be associated with various spheres of material and spiritual life.

Food is one of the most important conditions for human existence. It is one of the conditions of the material life of society, along with housing, clothing, geographical environment. Food is a link with the culture of the past, with the traditions and customs of peoples. Food is the basis of human life, a universal category of life support, a source of energy, without which life is impossible. Each culture has its own characteristics of consumption, preparation and recipes. This is the element of material culture in which traditional features are preserved more than others, the ideas of the people about their national specifics are most associated with it. Such a reality as food is a source of information not only about the life of the people and their perception of taste, color, shape, size, etc., but also, thanks to the nomination, provides information about linguistic trends due to both linguistic and extralinguistic factors.

The present study is devoted to the establishment of common and individual features in equivalent semantic groups, united by the meaning "food", in Russian and French.

The work uses a typological (comparative) method, actively used by scientists in contrastive linguistics (Katsnelson S. D., 1986, 298 e.; Katsnelson S. D., 1972, 216 e.; Rozhdestvensky Yu. V., 1969, 286 e.; Uspensky B. A., 1970, p. 13; Uspensky B. A., 1965, 286 e.; Greenberg J. H., 1957, pp. 68-77; Greenberg J. H., 1974, pp. 108-114; Lehrer A., 1974, 225 p.; Sella H.J., 1995, pp. 273-325 and others). Comparative typology compares two, three or more languages in order to detect isomorphisms and allomorphisms in them (Arakin V.D., 1989, p. 259; Gak V. G., 1983, 287 e.; Zelenetsky A. Ya., 1983, 240 e.; Koshevaya I. G., Dubovsky Yu, 126 p., etc.). Isomorphisms and allomorphisms are found at any level of the linguistic hierarchy, including in lexical semantics. However, it is in the field of lexical semantics that comparative typology is the least developed.

The identification and description of allomorphic features in the semantics of lexical units of different languages leads to the identification of lexico-semantic types of languages due to the existence of individual features in them, and the establishment of isomorphic features leads to the identification of universal properties that characterize the lexico-semantic systems of different languages. The existence of universals, obviously, is explained by the general structure of the perceptual-cognitive apparatus of a person and the general extralinguistic world. To answer the question of how these factors influence the formation of universal categories and why, despite its general structure, cognitive linguistics strives within the framework of the theory of categorization. A review of works on the problems of categorization indicates the importance of these processes for the cognition of human cognitive activity (Lakoff J., 1995, p. 43-184; Manerko L. A., 2000, p. 30-37; Manerko L. A., 2000 No. 2, pp. 39-51; Belyaevskaya E. G., 2000, pp. 9-14; Boldyrev N. N., 2001, 123 e.; Lakoff. In modern linguistics, there are two main areas in which the study of linguistic meaning is carried out: the semantics of invariants (component semantics) and the semantics of prototypes. The main provisions of the component theory are the statements:

- 1) the semantic space of the language is discrete;
- 2) the set of elements in this space is finite and observable, and the number of combinations is infinite;
- 3) language elements (semes) can be described as combinations of semantic components (semes) (Shafikov S. G, 1998, 196 f.). Modern science pays great attention

to the comparative analysis of languages and cultures. The active process of awareness of one's individuality, cultural identity makes this phenomenon natural. The attention of public consciousness is drawn to those areas and sectors that allow each people to supplement or develop the idea of the specifics of the national path within the framework of the general course of civilization, to determine the value of their culture and the originality of the language. A special role in this is played by contrastive linguistics, which convincingly and convincingly shows similarities and differences in the languages and cultures of peoples.

In the same organization of lexical units, the TG "food" in Russian. 55 individual semes (77.46%) are distinguished in the language, in French language - 68 (95.77%), 3 semes act as single ones in Russian - 4.23% ("cooking conditions" - in the meanings of LSG lexical units "names of first courses"; "additional function" - in the meanings of LSG lexical units "names of bakery products; "biological characteristics of reality" - in the meanings of LSG lexical units "names of second courses"); in French 17 - 23.94% ("quality of the base component" - in the meanings of the LSG lexical units "names of the second courses", LSG "names of the third courses"; dishes"; "territorial affiliation of the base component" - in the meanings of LSG lexical units "names of third courses"; "size of the base component" - in the meanings of LSG lexical units "names of third courses"; "cooking characteristics" - in the meanings of LSG lexical units "general names of food"; "method of serving" - in the meanings of lexical units LSG "general names of food", LSG "names of condiments", LSG "names of milk and dairy products", LSG "names of second courses", LSG "names of third courses", LSG "names of national and regional food"). This provision confirms the thesis about the concretization of meaning in French, in which the presence of individual semes indicates the desire of the language to differentiate meanings not only in the original units of the lexical corpus of the modern language, but also. in borrowings.

Comparison languages differ in taxonomic depth, i.e. quantity; general and individual differential terms. The existence of common (universal) terms is due to the very nature of the meaning, its model and generators; sources that are common for all languages and all units of the language. This explains the difference in the quantitative and qualitative composition of the language structures of the ways "names of food" in Russian and French.

REFERENCES:

1. Crystal, David (ed.), *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of the English Language* (Cambridge, 2003) ISBN 0-521-53033-4
2. Gould, Rebecca Ruth (2018). "Sweetening the Heavy Georgian Tongue: Jāmī in the Georgian-Persianate World". In d'Hubert, Thibaut; Papas, Alexandre (eds.). *Jāmī in Regional Contexts: The Reception of 'Abd al-Raḥmān Jāmī's Works in the Islamicate World, ca. 9th/15th-14th/20th Century*. Brill. ISBN 978-9004386600.
3. Matthee, Rudi (2009). "Was Safavid Iran an Empire?". *Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient*. Brill. 53 (1–2): 233–265. doi:10.1163/002249910X12573963244449. S2CID 55237025.
4. McArthur, Tom (ed.), *The Oxford Companion to the English Language* (Oxford, 1992), ISBN 0-19-280637-8